

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A477

11 September 1996

OXICOA — TACIA

ADDENDUM

The correct dates for each of the flights
are as follows:-

475	9 September 1996
476	10 September 1996
477	11 September 1996
478	13 September 1996
479	16 September 1996
480	17 September 1996
481	19 September 1996

TACIA OXICOA AUG-SEPT 96 Flight Summary

Prepared by: Andrew Kaye and Hannah Richer

[1] A475 9/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 1 2 hr 40 min

A short test flight for the chemistry instrumentation was carried out. The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). After initial concerns about the NO background, the NO_x instrument was found to operate satisfactorily on the two available channels (NO and NO₂).

An anticyclone centred to the west of the UK provided possible TACIA type weather. However, delays, due to incomplete airworthiness certification, meant that there was insufficient time to search for plumes from the UK. However, a small local plume was encountered in the Bristol Channel (51.36N, 4.12E).

Data from this flight could possibly be used to validate emission data from South Wales.

[2] A476 10/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 2 4 hr 30 min

Instruments performed as in the previous test flight: The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). The NO background had improved and the NO_x instrument was generally found to operate well on the two channels (NO and NO₂). However, on reaching maximum altitude difficulties were encountered on controlling the flow rate in the NO₂ channel.

A persistent anticyclone centred to the west of the UK again provided TACIA type conditions. However, delays, due to instrument requirements, meant that there was limited time to search for plumes from the UK. However, cross wind runs were carried out at an interval of approximately 60 miles along the SW coast. Trajectory analysis is to be carried out to determine whether the same air mass was sampled twice. However, no particularly notable plumes could be distinguished from the ozone, carbon monoxide and formaldehyde data. However, useful background information was obtained.

[3] A477 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 00 min

The presence of an occluded frontal system over Norway/North Sea facilitated the study of three different airmasses.

Profiles were successfully flown on both sides of the warm front, but there was not sufficient time to travel to the northern edge of the cold frontal surface. However the lowest levels of the second stack may have been north of the front.

Ozone, formaldehyde and PAN instruments worked well, but the CO background problem was not corrected and the NO_x NO₂ channel flow problem had not been resolved.

[4] A478 11/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 3 2 hr 56 min

Thursday 12 September was used to install the NO_x converters and rectify the CO instrument. The CO work was successful. However the NO_x converters took longer than expected to complete. This resulted in a delayed take off.

Although primarily a TACIA instrument test flight the opportunity was taken to characterise the Arctic Maritime air mass over the North Sea. This effectively completed the work started on A477.

The chemistry kit performed as well as could be expected given the reduced warm up times available. The ozone pump switched off unexpectedly during the flight which caused a loss of data until the problem was identified.

[5] A479 11/9/96 TACIA 5 hr 40 min

There was a high pressure centred over the North Sea on this day which gave rise to continental outflow in the south-west approaches.

A very successful trial of the TACIA flying pattern, with two stacks being flown to sample continental air. A double inversion (875 and 950 mbar) was identified effectively capping pollutants and isolating them from the ocean surface sinks. Elevated levels of aerosol, CO (170 ppb), NO (40 ppt), NO₂ (400 ppt) and O₃ (65 ppb) were noted in this layer. Another interesting parcel of air was also sampled at higher altitudes (6 - 8 km). This air parcel was characterised by high levels of CO and aerosol. All the chemistry instrumentation performed well and the flight will provide a valuable contribution to the TACIA experiment.

[6] A480 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 04 min

An anticyclone was centred to the north of the North Sea, such that continental plumes from northern Europe were reaching southern England across the North Sea. The same anticyclone was investigated during flight A479, at which time the high was centred over the UK.

The aim of this flight was to characterise air parcels within the anticyclone: both air parcels with recent continental influence and those with mainly marine back trajectories were studied. The highest pollutant concentrations of the campaign were measured during this flight in the boundary layer near Boscombe Down and in the marine boundary layer in the southern North Sea.

The marine boundary layer was distinct from the rest of the troposphere by a low level inversion. A slightly higher inversion was also apparent in profiles carried out north of 54 N. Interestingly, the seemingly typical vertical structure was not found in the southern North Sea: only the marine inversion was present.

A plume was encountered in the marine boundary layer at the first sampling region and elevated NO_x, NO_y and CO were observed with a corresponding decrease in ozone, indicating recent anthropogenic inputs. Profiles throughout the lowest 6000 ft of the atmosphere, whilst travelling northward, indicated some chemically aged parcels of air with elevated ozone, CO and NO_y. Haze layers were also visible. However, most of the air was generally clean. Further North, haze layers were less frequent, but layers with elevated ozone were still apparent. Elevated CO with a corresponding decrease in ozone indicated some recent pollution in the marine boundary layer at 57.2 N and 0.8 E.

All the chemistry instruments performed well during the flight. In particular, the peroxide measurements were found to show similar features to the calculated peroxide. Pitch, roll and yaw manoeuvres were carried out in order to test the NO_x inlets: preliminary results indicated that there were no large effects.

[7] A481 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight/NO_x test 6 hr 16 min

An attempt was made at an airmass characterization flight. However, within an hour of take off, the peroxide and CO instruments had failed completely and the NO_x was only functioning at 50%. After consultation with the instrument operators it was decided that useful tests could still be carried with the operational NO_x channels and the flight plan was changed to a NO_x test flight. Several NILU and MRF bottles were also filled for analysis of hydrocarbons and possibly CO.

However, it is interesting to note that, at one point, air of stratospheric origin was encountered: we were frustrated by the lack of a complete suite of instruments. Recently polluted air and air which was chemically aged, as indicated by ratios of NO_x/NO_y and ozone, were both sampled. Useful data on emissions from north eastern Europe may have been gained.

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 477

DATE: 11 109196

Take off: 1005

Landing: 1605

Aircraft Scientist	: A KAYE + H RICHER	Captain	: SQUADRO' BRIAN
Flight Leader	: D PERCIVAL	Co-pilot	: FLT LT M PURSE
Others	2) : M PICHERING	Navigator	: FLT LT J CANNING
O ₃	: S KENT	Engineer	: MENG K GUICH
NOX ₂	: K DEWEY, S BAGUIE	Loadmaster	: FLT SGT P JONES
CO	: S HESSLER, H GERBIG		
H ₂ O ₂	: B BANDY, L GARDINAS		
BOTTLES	: D TIDDEMAN		

Trials Instructions TACIA : MRF 13

Operating area : NORTH NORTH SEA

General synoptic situation

TIME: RZ

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p style="text-align: center;">6 \</p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 of 3 2 of 3 2 2</p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
	<p>SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 5</p>	<p>Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log <i>BOTTLE FILLER</i> 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 3 each</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

FLIGHT REPORT A477 11/09/96 TACIA

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading
10:03:09				TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN		
10:33:18	(14)	10:47:58	(15)	Run 1	FL130	020° Calibrations 250 kt IAS
11:09:57	(16)	11:22:08	(17)	Profile 1	FL190 FL050	090° 1000'/min
11:22:08	(17)	11:29:43	(18)	P 1 cont	FL050 50 ft	270° 500'/min Sea State 5
				First Stack		
11:30:56	(19)	11:39:59	(20)	Run 2	500 ft	220°
11:43 18	(21)	11:51:12	(22)	Run 3	3300'	030° Above Cu below Sc
11:58:47	(23)	12:05:59	(24)	Run 4	FL110	210° Between Sc layers
12:06:55	(25)	12:10:07	(26)	Run 5	FL116	190° In Sc
12:11:57	(27)	12:17:11	(28)	Run 6	FL136	085° Between Sc layers
12:21:33	(29)	12:31:02	(30)	Run 7	FL175	360° Above main Sc
				Saw Tooth moving North to Edge of Frontal Zone		
12:34:01	(31)	12:53:18	(32)	Profile 2.1	FL175 50 ft	300° 1000'/min Sea State 5
12:53:18	(32)	13:09:07	(33)	Profile 2.2	50 ft FL155	315° 1000'/min
13:09:07	(33)	13:25:41	(34)	Profile 2.3	FL155 50 ft	315° 1000'/min Sea State 5
13:25:41	(34)	13:34:22	(35)	Profile 2.4	50 ft FL080	355° 1000'/min
				Profile Down to Start Next Stack		
13:51:03	(37)	14:05:41	(38)	Profile 3	FL150 50 ft	200° 1000'/min Sea State 4
14:06:38	(39)	14:16:37	(40)	Run 8	500ft	100°
14:18:03	(41)	14:23:03	(42)	Run 9	2000'	280°
14:29:34	(46)	14:34:33	(47)	Run 10	FL080	100°
14:36:58	(48)	14:20:01	(49)	Run 11	FL100	280°
14:47:40	(51)	14:57:38	(53)	Run 12	FL150	100°
15:00:22	(54)	15:15:25	(55)	Run 13	FL140	190° Calibration Run 250 kt IAS
				Transit to Boscombe		
16:04:28				LAND AT Boscombe Down		
16:10:42				Data off. Shut down at 51°09.88N 001°44.66W		

A477 11-SEP-96 Height time series

MRF13

OXICOA VI: Air Mass Characterization Experiments

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To characterize the atmospheric chemical composition of the airmass. The data collected will be added to a systematically collected airmass data base. The data base will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere..

LOCATION: ~~SW approaches and West of Scotland~~ NORTH SEA .

WEATHER: Tropical and polar maritime air reaching the UK.

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Boscombe and transit to operational area as convenient. *FL30*
- [2] Execute a profile from FL200 to 50ft in cloud free air, if possible, @1,000ft/min down.
- [3] Execute a stepped racetrack pattern at levels specified by aircraft scientist. 5 minute runs.

500, *4000*, *115*, *132*, *170*, _____, _____.

- [4] Transit to new area and repeat [2] & [3] as time permits
- [5] Transit back to Boscombe Down as convenient.

AIRCRAFT FLYING PROGRAMME

DATE 11th September

FLIGHT NO A477

FTI MRF 13 TACIA

Aircraft scientist H Richer
Flight leader D Percival
Cloud physics M Pickering
PAN/Ozone J Kent
NOXY K Dewey / S Baguitte
CO S Kessler / K Gerbig
Peroxide B Bandy / L Gardinas
Bottle Sampler D Tiddeman
+ A Kaye / ~~P Monks~~

Pre-flight clearance D Boyd / J Pantrey dep 0730L
FTOs depart F'boro 0745L

Briefing 0900L

Take off 1100L

Return 1730L

Chris O' Brian -PI
M Purse 12
Ken Quick E
John Conroy R
Pete Jones L

Press RETURN for next display (H for help)

TODAY 10-SEP-1996 11:50

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A477

Date: 110496

A/S Name: KAYL

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for3.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state periodINDEF.....

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of ProjectACSOIE/TACIT.....

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?INDEF.....

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? ..MRF.....

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Young H. Richter

Project: AOSCE Date: 11/21/46

Flight No: A477 Page 1 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:14:09		Transit	5.1	P	1	51.44	-1.66	Small cir field ahead some Albes. above.	
10:20:13		Transit	10.0	P	4	51.85	-1.62	3/8 small cir below Sc 4/8 Sc above.	170
10:24:28		Transit	9.9	P	41	52.46	-0.02	in cloud. and bumpy	
10:31:24		TRANS	11.6	P	13	52.54	0.73	into upper cloud layer.	
10:33:17		R1	13.0	P	13	52.65	-0.69	4/8 Sc below broken cir above. Some contrails visible above.	33 12 46
10:42:00	14	R1	1300	P	27	53.38	-0.33	4/8 Sc cloud below and above.	
10:48:00	15	R1 cloud	1300	P	61	53.70	0.07	1/8 cloud below 7/8 above.	
10:53:07		Trans.	17.6	P	49	53.89	0.64	8/8 Sc below Some Ci Above.	
11:04:01	16	P1s	1900	P	79	54.54	2.70	Sc below 5/8 Ci above clear ahead.	170
11:12:43		P1	15.8	P				into cloud	132
								1500 Top of cloud.	
								14900 Bot of top cloud	
								13100 Top of middle cloud.	
								12500 Bot of middle cloud.	115
								10500 Top of bot cloud.	
								-6100 Bot of Bot cloud.	1300b top of cir

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Konye H. Richer

Project: ACSE

Date: 11/09/96

Flight No: 477

Page 2 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:24:50	R7	R1	3K	R	87	54.57	4.284	Small on below complex cloud Deck.	
11:24:42	R8	R1e	50 ft	R	266			1015 sea state 5.	
11:30:58		R2	500		217	54.55	3.888	Aircraft 170-180 cc. Drizzle 1000m - 1400m	
11:34:58		R2e	500		232	54.10	3.50		
11:45		R2	3300		27	54.31	3.56	Rain on windows. extending rear as it leads into clearer air.	
11:51:12		R3e	3300		23	54.66	3.98	Small on below <u>Sc. deck above</u> .	
11:58:47		R4	110	FL	220	54.62	4.01	Sc. above and below light ahead.	
12:03:52		R4	110	FL	224	54.37	3.75	in cloud.	
12:06:04		R4e	110	FL	209	54.26	3.65	pulling up to get out of cloud.	
12:07:00		R5	116	F6	195	54.21	3.61	between cloud layers	
12:10:04		R5e	116	F6	195	54.06	3.54	cloud rising again about rear and head for next hill.	
12:11:59		R6	136	FL	30	54.06	3.26	between Sc below and above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kays H. Richer.*

Project: *ACSOE*

Date: *11/07/76*

Flight No: *A477*

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
<i>12:17:11</i>		<i>R6e</i>	<i>136</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>57.25</i>	<i>3.12</i>	<i>SC above and below. FL153 into cloud.</i>	
<i>12:21:32</i>		<i>R7</i>	<i>175</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>359</i>	<i>54.49</i>	<i>3.93</i>	<i>Complex SC below Alto cir above and some ci above</i>	
<i>12:30:06</i>		<i>R7e</i>	<i>175</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>348</i>	<i>53.86</i>	<i>3.90</i>	<i>just slipped into a bit of 40% ACSOE. Sc. Endrum can't turn to start Sunclock.</i>	
<i>12:39:01</i>		<i>P201</i>	<i>175</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>295</i>	<i>53.12</i>	<i>3.65</i>	<i>in S clock</i>	<i>Clouds base 2000ft</i>
		<i>P202</i>							
<i>12:53:20</i>		<i>P2.1-32</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>297</i>	<i>55.57</i>	<i>2.11</i>	<i>some precip at the bottom of prof. l.e.</i>	<i>1013 5</i>
								<i>1200 clouds base.</i>	
<i>12:57:47</i>			<i>46</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>4</i>			<i>incloud and Precipitation on window</i>	<i>7300 out of cloud.</i>
<i>13:02:38</i>			<i>8.8</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>296</i>	<i>55.76</i>	<i>1.43</i>	<i>Cloud</i> <i>Cloud Bank edge ahead.</i>	
<i>13:09:04</i>	<i>33</i>	<i>P2.3</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>311</i>	<i>55.97</i>	<i>0.07</i>	<i>Thin Alto cir above.</i>	<i>11000 back into cloud</i>
								<i>SC below some gaps ahead.</i>	<i>14200 out of cloud</i>
								<i>12200 TdCl.</i>	
								<i>11700 Bot of cloud.</i>	
								<i>11400 TdCl.</i>	
								<i>9500 clear of cloud check</i>	

Sc below 6500 ft

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye H. RICHER.

Project: ACSOE

Date: 11/09/96

Flight No: A477

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad.	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:25.4	34	P.24	50	R	309	56.46	0.18	Sc above. Surf. Pres 1013 S. state S.	
								2200 Base Top	
13:31.2		P.24e	80	R	345	56.80	-0.71	Sc <u>below</u> .	
								Transit to look for the edge of Front.	
13:42.5			8.7	R	346	57.38	-0.96	Climb to ^{FL} 150 in prep for Stack.	
13:51.03		P3	150	R	162	57.70	-1.17	hazy above 8/8 sc below. 15K. — 10K. —	
								Cloud Top 7000 ft. — 6500 out of cloud 6000 —	
								5400 — 4100 precip 3000 — 2000 5000	
14:05.7		P3	50	R	193	56.97	-1.34	Sc above Sunlight scattered ahead 1013 Sest 4.	
14:06		R8	500	R	93	56.91	-1.28	instrument zero's on this 10 min Run.	
14:16:30	40	R8e	500	R	91	56.85	-0.28	lighter nearing cloud edge.	
14:18:05	41	R9	2000	R	277	56.81	-0.32	Some precip.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Keye M. Richer

Project: ACSE Date: 11/09/46

Flight No: A477 Page 5 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:23:02	42	R9	2.1	FL	274	50.80	-0.76	Sc above Coastline 50 miles visible ahead.	
14:26:56								3600 clouds Base.	
14:29:36	46	R10	8.1	FL	92	56.76	-1.02	Sc below Ci Ci Stratus above.	
								47° Halo in Ci cloud. Keros obs. gaps in cloud to west.	
								Some cloud 14:34.	
14:37:37	47	R10	8.0	FL	93	56.72	-0.56		
14:36:58		R11	100	FL	276	56.66	-0.50	Sc below Ci Strato Ci above halo visible.	
								cloud edge visible ahead. (West)	
14:41:57		R 11 11	100	FL	274	56.64	-0.97	Sc below cloud edge ahead ci above. front?	
14:47:46		R 11 12	150	FL	94	56.58	-1.26	14,700 → 20-30 ppt. zeros at 14:50	
14:57:37		R12	150	FL	104	56.42	-0.17	Ci Above Sc below.	
15:00:20 14:57:37		R13	140	FL	184	56.35	-0.19	240 Kts Calibration Transit towards home.	

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A477 Date: 120996 User: HAYE / RICHIER
Interactive by: D PERCIUAC
Date: 120996

Renav

TALMAN FILTERING USED.

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

$$a = -0.3517 \text{E} + 1$$

$$b = + 0.2070 \text{E} - 2$$

$$c = + 0.7358 \text{E} - 6$$

LWC

OK

Heimann / Barnes

OK

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR.	EXPECTED VALUE
0910	FL NO	1	Hex	0477	A477		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0091	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0125	091125	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	12-713	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
		4	0	9	5		
	LATC	160	Dec	000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	000			Longitude
0912							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: PRE-FLT

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0913	TWCD	70	2693	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1079	/		2000-3480	< min
	TSAM	72	0127	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2399	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2250	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2069	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2133	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1020	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	2043	/			
	EV2V	171	2043	/			
	NPWR	172	3421	/			
	EVIC	173	3962	/			
0920	EV2C	174	3168	/			

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon <i>swt</i>		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	On / Off	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon <i>swt</i>		

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1124	FL NO	1	Hex	477	A477	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0112	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0426	112426	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0017	17	/	Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
			H	0	9	5	
	LATC	160	Dec	0620	54.56 N		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0048	4.224 E		Longitude
1126							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL110

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1200	TWCD	70	1591	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2541	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1324	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2659	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2239	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1917	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1141	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1018	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	3477				
	EV2V	171	3139				
	NPWR	172	2694				
	EVIC	173	4016				
1200	EV2C	174	3948				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMS	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK Flight No: 4477 Date: 1109~~99~~ 96. Page.....of 3
for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1312	REF +	5	567	/			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2855	/			Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	2415	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1121	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	FL100			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2725	9.5	FL095		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	4095				
	A/S	9	1307	120			As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1512	425	292		
	UP2S	82	1092	182	143		
	UIRS	83	0551	-290	1557		
	UP1Z	84	150	/			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	139	/			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	214	/			Approx 2061
1327	UP1T	87	2641	9			As IAT
	UP2T	88	2661	9	12.6		As IAT
	UIRT	89	000				As IAT
1502	LP1S	91	0891	300	✓ 300		
	LP2S	92	0653	130	127		
	LIRS	93	491	-314	1552		
	LP1Z	94	0147	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0157	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	0485	3202			Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2826	2			As IAT
	LP2T	98	2787	4	4.6		As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000				As IAT
	J/W	42	1029	0			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	XXXX				
	HYGR	58	2041	-14	-14.4		
	HYCC	59	0747	/			696-901
	FDEW	138	1624	-15.55	✓		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	0602				
	DTF	10	1583	5			
	DTC	11	5		5.9		
	NDF	23	1353	4			same as De-Iced
	NDFC	24	5				
	INCT	48	4045				
HEIM	CGN	149	1942				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	1272	/			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	1326	/			0640-1880 < min
	O3	100	0163	/			
	O3P	106	2060	969			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	1742				
	O3F	114	735				
	MCHO	150	325				

142 PRIC 2342
151 ORGO 0013
152 H202 0073
154 CO 1227
185 P4W 1376
186 PLOC 1380

187 PTRN 1377
188 PFLO 0428
145 FIFL 1054
146 F1PR 1280
197 F2FL 1434

199 192 F2 PR 1566
175 NIRS 0639
176 N1UP 991
177 N8TS 476
178 NRTS 1024
179 NRTS 1033

181 NRTS 1048
182 NRTS 1074
183 NRTS 1087
184 NRTS 1104

End 15 38

Flight Leaders' ~~Pre~~/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1538	FL NO	1	Hex	0477	A477	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0153	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0855	153855	✓	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0055	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				4	0	9	5
	LATC	160	Dec	0598	52.624N	/	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4092	0°096W	/	Longitude
1540							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL100.

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1540	TWCD	70	1717	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2501	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1302	/		0840-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2658	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2240	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1631	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1488	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1018	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	3482				
	EV2V	171	3136				
	NPWR	172	2706				
	EVIC	173	4019				
	EV2C	174	4010				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

 Flight No **A 477**.....

 Date **11 04 96**.....

 Page of ...**2**....

Video Tape
No. A477 #1
Ends 1310
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	51°04.85N	51°04.85N
Long	001°44.65W	001°44.65W
Time	0822	0823
Status	4+5 CT	ALLIGN

DRS recording to HORACE (y)/n
HORACE recording to disc (y)/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports (y)/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
081051				DATA ON						
095040				sat E NAV						
095530				POWER TRANSFER.					3421	
100309				TAKE OFF		BOSCOMBE DOWN				340/08
				START	RUN	1				
103318	14	FL130	1013	020	230	-8.1	-9.6	OFF		356/13
				END	RUN	1				
104758	15	FL130	1013	060	250	-8.5	-10.5	OFF		257/12
				START	PI					
110957	16	FL290	1013	080	180	-18.6	-27.8	OFF	1000	331/14
				INT	PI					
112208	17	FL050	1013	090	180	2.5	2.7	OFF	500 _{min}	321/7
				END	PI					
112943	18	500 ^{FL}	1015	270	180	12.4	10.0	OFF		301/10 SS=5
				START	RUN	2				
113056	19	500 ^{FL}	1015	220	180	11.3	9.2	OFF		292/11
				Missed Cal	PI					
				END	RUN	2				
113954	20	500 ^{FL}	1015	220	180	11.2	9.0	OFF		

Video Tape	
No.	AH 77# 1
Ends	1310
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	54° 13.35N	54° 16.68N
Long	003° 33.29E	3° 34.88E
Time	114209	114249
Status	4x5 dt	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
									<i>cloud 1000 ft/in</i>	
				START	R2				<i>Above Cu / Below Sc</i>	
114318	21	3300	1015	035	185	4.7	4.9	OFF		305/7
				END	R3					
115112	22	3300	1015	030	185	5.1	4.1	OFF		310/9
				<i>Heaven Cal OP</i>						
		FL 110		START	R4				<i>Below Sc layers.</i>	
115847	23	1013	1013	225	190	-5.6	-7.5	OFF		311/12
				END	R4					
120554	24	FL 110	1013	210	180	-7.2	-6.6	OFF		310/12
				START	R5					
120855	25	FL 116	1013	185	190	-7.2	-7.2	OFF		309/11
				END	R5					
121007	26	FL 116	1013	190	185	-7.3	-7.4	OFF		309/11
				START	R6				<i>IN Betwⁿ Between cloud layers.</i>	
121157	27	FL 136	1013	085	180	-10.0	-12.2	OFF		327/11
				END	R6					
121711	28	FL 136	1013	002	180	-11.5	-12.2	OFF		333/13
				START	R7				<i>Above main Sc deck.</i>	
122133	29	FL 175	1013	360	190	-18.7	-24.5	OFF		342/11
				END	R7					
123102	30	FL 175	1013	360	180	-19.1	-16.4	OFF		342/14

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

 Flight No A 477.....

 Date 11 09 96.....

 Page 2 of 2.....

Video Tape	
No.	A477 HI
Ends	1310
	Changed to #2
	(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	55° 22 33	55 24 20 W
Long	2° 46.23 E	20 39.01 E
Time	1244 59	NAV
Status	OK	OK

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				START	P2.1					
123401	31	FL175	1013	300	180	-17.2	-16.0	OFF	1000/m	
	5318			END	P2.1	/START	P2.2		1000/m	
1288	32	5000	1013	305	180	12.3	11.8	OFF		287/9
				Human Cal	PO9					5
				END	P2.2	START	P2.3			
130907	33	FL155	1013	315	180	-10.3	-15.8	OFF		324/15
				END	P2.3	//	START	P2.4	1000/m	
132541	34	5000	1013	320	180	13.5	9.4	OFF		291/10
				Human Cal	PO9					SS = 5
				END	P2.4					
133422	35	FL090	1013	355	180	0.5	-1.3	OFF		321/17
				TRANSIT	NORTH.					
133900	36			Human Cal	Cloud Top Temp					PO5
				START	P3					
135103	37	FL150	1013	180	180			OFF	1000/m	
				END	P3					
140541	38	5000	1013	200	175	13.3	10.5	OFF		295/7
										SS = 4
				START	R	S				
140638	39	500	1013	100	180	13.1	8.4	OFF		300/10

Video Tape
No. A177#2
Ends 16 10
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	56°51'46" N	56°50'95" N
Long	005°09' W	000°43'31" W
Time	1410	1412
Status	NAU OK	NAU

DRS recording to HORACE	(y/n)
HORACE recording to disc	(y/n)
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
					END	R8			
141637	40	500 ^{ft}	1013	100	180	11.7	9.6	OFF	291/10
				START	R9				
141803	41	2000	1013	280	185	8.3	7.7	OFF	313/17
				END	R9				
142303	42	2000	1013	280	180	8.0	7.5	OFF	310/18
				START	R10				
142434	46	FL080	1013	100	190	1.5	-0.1	OFF	321/15
				END	R10				
143433	47	FL080	1013	100	180	1.6	0.0	OFF	317/14
				START	R11				
143650	48	FL100	1013	280	180	-2.6	-9.3	OFF	319/19
				END	R11				
144201	49	FL100	1013	280	180	-2.1	-12.2	OFF	323/20
144630	50	FL150		END	dist				
				START	R12				
144740	51	FL150	1013	100	180	-10.1	-38.5	OFF	340/21
				END	R12				
145738	53	FL150	1013	100	180	-11.3	-34.1	OFF	339/19
				START	R13				
150022	54	FL140	1013	280	245	-9.4	-18.8	OFF	328/20
				END	R13				
151525	55	FL140	1013	190	245	-8.3	-29.4	OFF	331/18
160424				LAST	Baseline				

VIDEO TAPE LOGFlight No A 477.....Project TACIA.....Date 11.09.96.....Tape No AH77#1 User KATE/ALICIA.....Retention Period INDEF.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
1010	0000	FFF	Tape On climb out to Operating Area
1104 57 112943		'	PROF1 FL140 → 50 ^{RC}
113056 113954		"	Run 2 50 ^{RC}
114318 115112		"	Run 3 3300
115847 120554		"	Run 4 FL110
120655 121007		"	Run 5 FL116
121157, 121711		'	Run 6 FL136
122137 123102.		"	Run 7 FL175
123401 125318		"	P 2-1 FL175 → 50 ^{RC}
125319 130907.		"	P 2-2 50 ^{RC} → FL155
			End of Tape.
			Changed to AH77#2

HERCULES VIDEO TAPE LOG

FLIGHT NO. A 477 ^{2 of 2}

PROJECT TACIA

DATE 11 : 09 : 96

TAPE NO. A477#2 USER KAYE/RICHER

RETENTION PERIOD INDEF

GMT	TAPE COUNTER	CAMERA POSITION	REMARKS
130800	0000	FFC	P 2.2 START OF TAPE
130907 132541		"	P 2.3 FLISS → 50 ^{RC}
132541 133422		"	P 2.4 50 ^{RC} → FLOPO
135103 140541		"	P 3 FL150 → 50 ^{RC}
140630 141637		"	Run 8 500 ^{RC}
141803 142303		"	Run 9 2000 ^{FT}
142934 143433		"	Run 10 FLOPO
143658 142001		"	Run 11 FL100
144748 145730		"	Run 12 FL150
150022 151525		"	Run 13 FL140.
161042		"	LAND BOSCOMBE DOWN
			End of Tape.

DATE _____

TI MRF _____

NAV CAROLINE

AIRFIELD R0

AIRFIELD R0 KR

R/W 23 W/V 330/15 TEMP +15 QNH 1021 QFE 1006

R/W 23 W/V 280/6 TEMP +18 QNH 1017 QFE 1003

WX HIL

WX Blue 2SK

ATC CL L/3000

ATC CL _____

T/O TIME 1110

LAND TIME 1401705

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1033 ¹⁸ 47 ⁵⁹	014	25	273	243	297	002/10	F130		N 52377 W 00408	R1
1109 ⁵⁷ 24 ⁴³	081	55	256	182	240	311/30	F190		N 53408 W 00040 N 54318 E 002378	R1
30 ⁵⁰ 34 ⁵⁹	217	66	178	181	180	290/21	560		N 54334 E 3366	R2
43 ¹⁸ 51 ¹²	028	60	193	185	195	305/12	3500		N 54101 E 03328 N 54110 E 03 36.9	R3
57 ⁵¹ 1205 ⁵⁴ 06 ⁵⁵	220	56	225	190	222	314/22	F110		N 54379 E 04014 N 54377 E 03112 N 54158 E 03418	R4
1210 ⁰⁷ 11 ⁵⁷ 17 ¹¹							F116 ✓		N 54128 E 339.3 N 54000 E 0336.6	R5
22 ³³ 31 ⁰²	071	55	231	180	220	328/19	F136		N 54025 E 03346	R6
34 ⁰¹ 53 ⁴⁸							F175		N 54123 E 03580 N . . E ?	R7
1309 ⁰¹ 25 ⁴¹	358	20	225	180	237	345/21	F175		N 55017 E 03576	R8
	302	-30	216	185	230	338/27	F175		N 55066 E 03425	R2.1
	297	28	154	171	180	308/23	50		N 55337 E 02092	R2
	311	143	21	182	23	331/37	F150		N 55513 E 00578	R3
						317/30	↗		N 56278 E 000913	R4
							F180		N 56448 W 00582	R5
1351 ⁰⁴ 1403 ⁴¹ 22	163	39	254	178	220	330/48	F150		N 57403 W 01081	R4
									N 56553 W 01169	R5

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUN
1406 ³⁰	094	55	202	180	180	301/19	500		N56531 W01144	R8
1637									N56491 W00831	—
1809	276	SP	165	183	190	314/32	2000		N56468 W00233	R9
2309									N56466 W00397	—
29 ³⁴	092	65	222	182	207	313/29	150 150		N56434 W01060	R10
34 ³⁵									N56409 W00322	—
36 ³⁸	205	SP	185	182	210	316/32	F100		N56374 W00234	R11
42 ⁰¹									N56369 W00524	—
47 ⁴⁰	043	65	252	180	240	320/39	F100		N56328 W01195	R12
57 ³⁸									N56229 W0070	—
1500 ²	180	3P	343	250	300	328/37	F140		N56098 W00131	R13
1525									N56440 W00844	—

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. 417 Date 11/9/96

Sheet no. 1

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE		True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME		
1	APL P4 B3	Run 1		500ft	11:30:56	11:35:15	9994	7.1 bar
2	APL P4 B4	Run 3		3300ft	11:43:20	11:46:00	8994	7.1 bar
3	APL P4 B5	Run 4		FL110	11:55:57 11:55:57	12:04:15	870	7 bar
4	APL P4 B1	Run 5		FL116	12:07:10	12:09:20 12:07:10	855	5.9 bar
5	APL P4 B6	Run 6		FL136	12:11:56	12:13:45	805	7 bar
6	APL P4 B11	Run 7		FL175	12:21:33 12:21:33	12:27:20		3 bar average pressure
7	APL P4 B10	Run 8		500ft	14:06:40	14:14:40	9993	7.2 bar
8	APL P4 B7	Run 9		1000ft	14:18:41	14:20:41	939	7.2 bar
9	APL P4 B9	Run 10		8000ft	14:21:34	14:31:33	752	7.1 bar
10	APL P4 B12	Run 11		10000	14:36:53	14:39:11	696	7.1 bar
11	APL P4 B8	Run 12		15000	14:47:40	14:59:14	576	6.7 bar
12	APL P4 B5	Run 13		16000	14:59:00	15:02:55	505	5.9

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A477

DATE: 11 / 09 / 96 .

MRF 13

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	✓ / / /		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/ / / / / / / / / / / / /		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	/ / -NOZ / / -NOZ / / / / /		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX ✓	/ / /		
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	/ / / /		

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

A477

11-SEP-96

12:30:00

029 Ω

54.98

3.91 FR P

HDG deg T 355.	SPR mb 516.	PHGT kft 17.5	TAS knots 246.	TAT C -19.1	DEW C -17.8	WIND deg m/s 343/13	
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	---	------------	---

A477 11-SEP-96 12:08:36 025 54.12 3.60 AS F

HDG deg	SPR m/s	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
187.	648.	11.9	220.	-7.7	-7.6	305/12

CO MR 18.50 OZONE MR 43.25

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
					WIND		UCID

A477 11-SEP-96 11:55:45 022 -- 54.80 4.23 AS P

160. 750. 8.1 201. -3.2 -2.6 305/10

-202 MR 2.55 0000 0000

1150 1155 1152 1155

A477

11-SEP-96

11:47:03

021 2

54.47

3.76 FR P

HDG degT 28.	SPR mb 898.	PHGT kft 3.3	TAS knots 196.	TAT C 4.9	DEW C 5.1	WIND deg m/s 313/8
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10000.00
 8000.00
 6000.00
 4000.00
 2000.00
 0.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477

11-SEP-96

11:43:03

020 02

54.29

3.54 FR P

HDG degT 27.	SPR mb 901.	PHGT kft 3.2	TAS knots 189.	TAT C 5.0	DEW C 4.5	WIND deg m/s 315/ 6
--------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	---------------------------

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477 11-SEP-96 11:41:30 020 Ω 54.21 3.47 FR P

HDG degT 28.	SPR mb 961.	PHGT kft 1.4	TAS knots 185.	TAT C 8.6	DEW C 8.3	WIND deg m/s 315/ 6
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111.30 3.33 130NE MF 33.75 996

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477

11-SEP-96

11:39:51

019 Ω

54.18

3.51 ER P

HDG deg T 215.	SPR mb 997.	PHGT kft 0.5	TAS knots 186.	TAT C 11.3	DEW C 9.3	WIND deg m/s 295/10
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FEET	100.00	m	HQHO MP	238.00	ppb	ZONE MP	10.00	ppb
	0.00	250.00	500.00	750.00	1000.00	1250.00	10000.00	

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477

11-SEP-96

11:37:27

019 Ω

54.28

3.62 FR P

HDG deg T 215.	SPR mb 994.	PHGT kft 0.5	TAS knots 183.	TAT C 11.2	DEW C 8.7	WIND deg m/s 297/10
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477 11-SEP-96 11:30:03 018 Ω 54.58 3.95 RY P

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
268.	1002.	0.3	187.	12.0	9.5	303/11

GE DP

A | B | C | D | E | F | G | H

A477

11-SEP-96

11:18:03

016 Ω

54.56

3.53 FR P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
85.	701.	9.9	213.	-5.9	-5.1	315/ 7

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

H411

11-SEP-96

11:16:15

016 Q

54.56

3.34 FR P

Hdg deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
86.	646.	11.9	221.	-7.1	-7.5	330/g

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	VIDEO	HELP

A477 11-SEP-96 10:59:24 010 -- 04.10
 HDG 50. deg
 SPR 485. mb
 PHGT 19.0 kft
 TAS 313. knots
 TAT -18.6 C
 DEW -28.4 C
 WIND 339/13 deg m/s

A	H	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A477 11-SEP-96 10:57:12 015 -- 34.05 1.00 F K F

HDG deg	SPR ms	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg
51.	485.	19.0	300.	-18.6	-26.8	340/13

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A477 11-SEP-96 10:55:51 015 Q 53.99 0.00 CR

HDG deg 51.	SPR m ^b 485.	PHGT kft 19.0	TAS knots 278.	TAT C -18.8	DEW C -27.6	WIND deg 339/13
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A477 11-SEP-96 10:54:12 015 23.32 0.10 GR

HDG deg	SPR m/s	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
49.	501.	18.3	260.	-18.0	-23.6	343/11

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A477 11-SEP-96 10:30:07 010 -- 03.11

HDG degT 59.	SPR mb 577.	PHGT kft 14.8	TAS knts 277.	TAT C -12.6	DEW C -12.7	WIND deg 344/17
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477

11-SEP-70

10:43:00

OUT

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
29.	620.	13.0	311.	-8.0	-10.9	359/15

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477

11-SEP-70

10:41.7L

017

HDG deg 16.	SPR mb 620.	PHGT kft 13.0	TAS knots 310.	TAT C -8.4	DEW C -9.9	WIND deg m/s 004/12
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33.1.00	33.1.00	33.1.00	33.1.00	33.1.00	33.1.00	33.1.00
1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00

0.00	25.00	50.00	75.00	100.00	125.00
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477

11-DEC-70

14:33:10

007

HDG deg 15.	SPR mb 620.	PKGT k ft 13.0	TAS knots 310.	TAT C -7.7	DEW deg -10.5	WIND deg 003/13
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38.40 ppb

C OZONE MR 12.50

-5.98

TWC DEWP

m

3353.79

30.00

12.50

-5.00

-22.50

-10.00

-57.50

-5.00

5000.00

0:00

0:10

0:20

0:30

100.00

200.00

300.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477 11-SEP-96 10:36:54 014 Ω 52.91 -0.58 RV P
 HDG 14. SPR 620. PHGT 13.0 TAS 310. TAT -7.9 DEW -9.8 WIND 006/13
 degT mb kft knots C C deg m/s

GE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

H411

11 DEC 70 10.00.00

HDG degT 15.	SPR mb 620.	PHGT kft 13.0	TAS knots 307.	TAT C -8.1	DEW C -9.7	WIND deg m/s 359/13	
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FREE HGT 0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 5.00
 5000.00 4000.00 3000.00 2000.00 1000.00 0.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477 11-SEP-96 10:32:39 013 Ω 52.60 -0.71 FC F

HQS deg	SPR m/s	PHGT kft	TAS kts	THT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
14.	633.	12.4	277.	-6.4	-10.8	002/13

GE DEWP -10.83 FL DEWP -15.75

H	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A477 11-SEP-96 13:35:21 035 56.82 -0.72 AS P

HDG deg	SPR m/s	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
345.	728.	8.9	237.	-0.2	-1.6	322/17

PRES HGT	ALT	POTE	K
2705.82	300.00	313.67	
370.00	300.00	310.00	5000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
CC	IC	UC	EM	7	00M	WT	000

A477

11-SEP-96

13:24:30

033

Ω

56.45

-0.16 FR P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
degT	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
309.	993.	0.6	187.	12.2	8.6	296/13

PRESS - FT 171.10 m 000NE MP 15.15 PPb 00 MP 8.00 00b
 0.00 25.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00

A477 11-SEP-96 12:52:48 031 Ω 55.57 2.13 FR P

HDG deg	SFR m/s	FHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
297.	1005.	0.2	184.	12.3	11.1	293/10

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477 11-SEP-96 12:51:45 031 -- 55.54 2.20 AS P

HDDG	ERR	FRGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	no	deg	knots	C	C	deg m/s
296.	989.	0.7	185.	10.9	10.6	294/12

FEES	HT	W	BT	PT	TE	TE
300.00	300.00	300.00	300.00	300.00	300.00	300.00
10000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
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A477

11-SEP-96

12:45:54

031 Ω

55.41

2.62 FR P

HDG deg T 296.	SPR mb 811.	PHGT kft 6.0	TAS knots 202.	TAT C 1.3	DEW C 1.1	WIND deg m/s 302/12	
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477 11-SEP-96 12:41:36 031 Ω 55.31 2.97 FR P

HDG degt 298.	SPR mb 690.	PHGT kft 10.3	TAS knots 211.	TAT C -5.8	DEW C -4.5	WIND des m/s 317/10
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477 11-SEP-96 12:37:57 031 Ω 55.22 3.29 FR P

HDG degT 297.	SPR mb 601.	PHGT kft 13.8	TAS knots 225.	TAT C -10.6	DEW C -15.9	WIND deg m/s 327/13
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477

11-SEP-96

12:35:30

031

Ω

55.16

3.52 FR P

HDG deg T 309.	SPR mb 548.	PHGT kft 16.0	TAS knots 243.	TAT C -15.7	DEW C -15.4	WIND deg m/s 341/13
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10000.00 10000.00
 8000.00 8000.00
 6000.00 6000.00
 4000.00 4000.00
 2000.00 2000.00
 0.00 0.00

0.00 250.00 500.00 750.00 1000.00 1250.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477 11-SEP-96 12:32:57 030 Ω 55.10 3.76 FR P

HDG deg 297.	SPR mb 517.	PHGT kft 17.5	TAS knots 231.	TAT C -19.1	DEW C -17.8	WIND deg m/s 339/13
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SE CF

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A477 11-SEP-96 15:00:48 054 Ω 56.15 -0.30 FR P

HDG deg 183.	SPR mb 595.	FHGT kft 14.0	TAS knots 308.	TAT C -9.3	DEW C -21.0	WIND deg m/s 328/19
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SEE -> 1333.33 m HEDGE MF 0.10 BR6 WED HEDG J. 21 999
 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00

3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00 3.00 1.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477

11-SEP-96

14:58:12

053

Ω

56.38

-0.15 FR P

HDG deg T 211.	SPR mb 595.	PHGT kft 14.0	TAS knots 287.	TAT C -10.6	DEW C -29.8	WIND deg m/s 323/20
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PRESS -97 1355.00 m QZONE MP 55.01 PR6 00 MP 135.50 PR6
 0.00 25.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00 5000.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A477 11-SEP-96 14:18:42 041 56.80 -0.37 FR P

HDG deg T 276.	SPR mb 939.	PHGT k ft 2.1	TAS knts 193.	TAT C 8.3	DEW C 7.9	WIND deg m/s 310/16	
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333 -07 333.10 m SECURE MF 13.33 ppb 30 MF 3017.33 985
 3.00 35.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00 5000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477 11-SEP-96 14:10:00 039 56.90 -0.97 AS P

994	0.5	187.	12.6	9.2	296 / 9
WIND	WIND	WIND	WIND	WIND	WIND

1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
2000.00	2000.00	2000.00	2000.00	2000.00	2000.00
3000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00	3000.00
4000.00	4000.00	4000.00	4000.00	4000.00	4000.00
5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00	5000.00

0.00	270.00	280.00	290.00	300.00	310.00	320.00	0.00
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
REFLECT	CHEM	700M					

A477 11-SEP-96 13:51:33 037 Ω 57.68 -1.15 FR P

HDG deg 163.	SPR mb 580.	PHGT kft 14.6	TAS knots 226.	TAT C -9.6	DEW C -36.7	WIND deg m/s 337/22
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1123.31 10 MP 1.00 896 32.11 898
 3.00 150.00 500.00 1000.00 1250.00 10000.00

0.00 55.00 50.00 100.00 125.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	#

A477

11-SEP-96

15:52:48

055 22 01.82

-1.44 FK F

HDG degT 197.	SPR mb 821.	PRGT kft 5.7	TAS knots 290.	TAT C 2.3	DEW C 1.8	WIND deg m/s 306/8
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A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A477 11-SEP-96 15:24:51 055 53.92 -0.60 FR H

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
216.	506.	18.0	318.	-15.5	-31.2	350/19

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A477 11-SEP-96 15:18:57 055 Ω 54.44 -0.34 FR P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
184.	531.	16.8	284.	-13.2	-30.2	340/18

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A477 11-SEP-96 15:15:54 055 02 54.72 -0.34 FR P

HDG degT 184.	SPR mb 584.	PHGT kft 14.5	TAS knots 300.	TAT C -8.5	DEW C -22.5	WIND deg m/s 332/19
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SE GEN# -22.51 OZONE VR 55.13

1450	1455	1500	1505	1510	1515
A	B	C	D	E	F
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM	VIDEO	HELP

A477 11-SEP-96 15:08:18 054 55.44 -0.32 FR P

HDG deg 184.	SPR m/s 596.	PHGT kft 14.0	TAS knots 315.	TAT C -8.8	DEW C -13.6	WIND deg m/s 329/18
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477 11-SEP-96 15:05:36 054 -0.30 FR F

HDG deg 184.	SPR m/s 596.	PHGT kft 14.0	TAS knots 316.	TAT C -9.5	DEW C -12.8	WIND deg 329/18
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A477 11-SEP-96 15:03:51 054 -- 00.00 -0.00 r r

HQG deg 184.	SPR mb 596.	PHGT kft 14.0	TAS knots 316.	TAT C -9.8	DEW C -12.6	WIND deg 329/19
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

02 171 1300 1995 SEP 11 11:15 AM

NETS 11 SEP 1996 1500 TR1 02

75337

MEIS 11 SEP 1996 1300 VISIT 002

MEIS 11 SEP 1996 1300 C

MEM 11 SEP 1966 1500 0151Z 08Z

MEM 11 SEP 1966 1

500-1000MB
 - - - THICKNESS DM.
 0 + - - - HEIGHT DM.
 00Z MED 11/ 9/96 VI 00Z MED 11/ 9/96 GMAIN 1 + 0

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE. 001

11 SEP '96 03:56

IR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.39.46
 CHART 13
 PHEASO EGR 0000Z

T 00Z WED 11/ 9/96 VT 00Z THUR 12/ 9/96 GMAIN T + 24
- - - THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

500-1000MB
500MB

SOLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 05:39:55

CHART 13

PHEE50 EGRR 0000Z

11 SEP '96 04:55

FSXX 007 12/9/96

FSXX EGR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 12 SEP 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 63°N, Grid Interval: 20m

11 SEP '96 04:38

** TOTAL PAGE 001 **
MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE.001

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX 521

11 SEP 96 04:38

ASXX EGRR.. MSLP. ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 11 SEP 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

A477.TXT

From 18Z 8/ 9/1996 to 15Z 11/ 9/1996

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 28-04-1996 13:14

A477 11-SEP-96

P1 FL190-50ft(110957-112943) + Stack1 50ft-FL175(112943-123102)

A477 11-SEP-96

P2.1 FL175-50ft(123401-125318) + P2.2 50ft-FL155(125318-130907)

A477 11-SEP-96

P2.3 FL155-50ft(130907-132541) + P2.4 50ft-FL080(132541-133422)

A477 11-SEP-96

P3 FL150-50ft(135103-140541) + Stack2 50ft-FL150(140541-145738)

A477 11-SEP-96 R1 FL130 From 103318-104758 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:21

A477 11-SEP-96 R1 FL130 From 103318-104758 Plotted 11-06-1996 16:21

A477 11-SEP-96 R1 FL130 From 103318-104758 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:21

A477 11-SEP-96 R1 FL130 From 103318-104758 Plotted 11-02-1996 16:21

A477 11-SEP-96 R1 FL130 From 103318-104758 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:21

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 881
Mean 621.103
Standard dev 0.386903
Max value 621.770
Min value 618.135

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 881
Mean 265.173
Standard dev 0.234835
Max value 265.679
Min value 264.546

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 881
Mean 262.843
Standard dev 0.482635
Max value 263.959
Min value 261.541

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 881
Mean 40.6836
Standard dev 1.78123
Max value 45.6592
Min value 37.9665

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 881
Mean 6.74716
Standard dev 12.2152
Max value 234.526
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 881
Mean 5.635726e-03
Standard dev 3.999816e-02
Max value 0.605614
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 881
Mean 3941.59
Standard dev 4.79243
Max value 3978.39
Min value 3933.35

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 881
Mean 53.1758
Standard dev 0.311704
Max value 53.6796
Min value 52.6346

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 881
Mean -0.394343
Standard dev 0.195429
Max value 4.811531e-02
Min value -0.678871

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 881
Mean -12.9140
Standard dev 0.981316
Max value -10.9552
Min value -15.7300

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 881
Mean -0.145093
Standard dev 1.21718
Max value 3.06273
Min value -2.40986

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 881
Mean -2.818201e-02
Standard dev 0.555172
Max value 1.09746
Min value -1.66393

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 881
Mean 12.9716
Standard dev 0.987062
Max value 15.9323
Min value 11.0372

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 0.643707

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 881
Mean 157.846
Standard dev 3.79765
Max value 161.337
Min value 138.348

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 22.6776

A477 11-SEP-96 P1 FL190-50ft From 110957-112943 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 16:24

A477 11-SEP-96 P1 FL190-50ft From 110957-112943 Plotted 11-01-1996 16:25

A477 11-SEP-96 P1 FL190-50ft From 110957-112943 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:25

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-01-1996 16:34

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-06-1996 16:35

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:35

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-04-1996 16:35

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:35

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:35

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:35

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL175 From 112943-123102 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:35

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 3680
Mean 743.783
Standard dev 175.302
Max value 1013.06
Min value 516.688

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 3680
Mean 269.782
Standard dev 10.3776
Max value 286.137
Min value 254.143

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 3680
Mean 268.470
Standard dev 10.7689
Max value 283.358
Min value 243.920

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 3680
Mean 43.4815
Standard dev 2.76202
Max value 51.2053
Min value 37.3041

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 3680
Mean 68.2220
Standard dev 86.4752
Max value 1802.07
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 3680
Mean 4.39214
Standard dev 12.8217
Max value 162.559
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 3680
Mean 2711.89
Standard dev 1877.02
Max value 5331.49
Min value 1.59497

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 3680
Mean 54.4330
Standard dev 0.245756
Max value 55.0254
Min value 53.9836

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 3680
Mean 3.87017
Standard dev 0.189510
Max value 4.27310
Min value 3.50576

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3680
Mean -7.27293
Standard dev 2.68397
Max value -2.54498
Min value -13.5975

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3680
Mean 6.55734
Standard dev 2.42772
Max value 11.8929
Min value 1.84502

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3680
Mean -0.761481
Standard dev 0.792849
Max value 1.66669
Min value -3.27515

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 3680
Mean 10.2632
Standard dev 1.91211
Max value 14.0742
Min value 5.41096

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 317.962

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 3680
Mean 108.247
Standard dev 10.4500
Max value 128.317
Min value 90.2198

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 354.766

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.1 FL175-50ft From 123401-125318 Plotted 11-01-1996 16:39

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.1 FL175-50ft From 123401-125318 Plotted 11-01-1996 16:39

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.1 FL1175-50ft From 123401-125318 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 16:39

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.2 50ft-FL155 From 125318-130907 Plotted 11-01-1996 16:42

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.2 50ft-FL155 From 125318-130907 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:42

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.2 50ft-FL155 From 125318-130907 Plotted 11-06-1996 16:42

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.3 FL155-50ft From 130907-132541 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:45

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.3 FL155-50ft From 130907-132541 Plotted 11-02-1996 16:45

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.3 FL155-50ft From 130907-132541 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:45

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.4 50ft-FL080 From 132541-133422 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 16:46

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.4 50ft-FL080 From 132541-133422 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:46

A477 11-SEP-96 P2.4 50ft-FL080 From 132541-133422 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:46

A477 11-SEP-96 Sawtooth run P2 From 123401-133422 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:55

A477 11-SEP-96 Sawtooth run P2 From 123401-133422 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:55

A477 11-SEP-96 Sawtooth run P2 From 123401-133422 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:55

A477 11-SEP-96 Sawtooth run P2 From 123401-133422 Plotted 11-04-1996 16:55

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 789.518
 Standard dev 138.144
 Max value 1010.95
 Min value 517.524

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 44.3155
 Standard dev 4.46088
 Max value 62.4012
 Min value 35.7963

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 2158.25
 Standard dev 1439.26
 Max value 5319.51
 Min value 19.1773

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean -9.28088
 Standard dev 3.07408
 Max value -1.88677
 Min value -16.4982

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 13.2458
 Standard dev 2.02967
 Max value 18.6700
 Min value 8.33619

DECIDED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 273.396
 Standard dev 7.67238
 Max value 286.813
 Min value 254.069

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 195.452
 Standard dev 263.286
 Max value 3485.83
 Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 55.8654
 Standard dev 0.464330
 Max value 56.7473
 Min value 55.1107

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 8.96344
 Standard dev 1.90913
 Max value 14.0150
 Min value 3.45672

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 104.328
 Standard dev 8.40477
 Max value 125.151
 Min value 88.4453

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 272.484
 Standard dev 8.77963
 Max value 285.024
 Min value 242.142

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 23.0780
 Standard dev 52.5205
 Max value 445.828
 Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 1.37455
 Standard dev 1.26693
 Max value 3.70798
 Min value -0.638209

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 3622
 Mean 0.279534
 Standard dev 2.41622
 Max value 3.81918
 Min value -4.45181

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 303.772

A477 11-SEP-96 P3 FL150-50ft From 135103-140541 Plotted 11-0d-1996 16:57

A477 11-SEP-96 P3 FL150-50ft From 135103-140541 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:57

A477 11-SEP-96 P3 FL150-50ft From 135103-140541 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:57

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL150 From 140541-145738 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:04

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL150 From 140541-145738 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:04

A477 11-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL150 From 140541-145738 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:04

FILE ERROR
EAGLE::TIDDEMAN
JOB 270
PLOT.LPS;14

%RMS-E-FNF, file not found
%SYSTEM-W-NOSUCHFILE, no such file

A477 11-SEP-96 R13 FL140 From 150022-151525 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:06

A477 11-SEP-96 R13 FL140 From 150022-151525 Plotted 11-06-1996 17:06

A477 11-SEP-96 R13 FL140 From 150022-151525 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:06

A477 11-SEP-96 R13 FL140 From 150022-151525 Plotted 11-01-1996 17:06

A477 11-SEP-96 R13 FL140 From 150022-151525 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:06

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 901
Mean 596.927
Standard dev 0.342526
Max value 597.318
Min value 594.868

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 901
Mean 264.332
Standard dev 0.739625
Max value 265.671
Min value 263.221

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 901
Mean 257.638
Standard dev 4.02804
Max value 263.698
Min value 244.785

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 901
Mean 45.3197
Standard dev 6.28148
Max value 62.5791
Min value 1.000000e-38

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 901
Mean 8.51031
Standard dev 9.19654
Max value 43.0196
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 901
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 901
Mean 4245.54
Standard dev 4.37982
Max value 4271.88
Min value 4240.54

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 901
Mean 55.4524
Standard dev 0.416604
Max value 56.1723
Min value 54.7342

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 901
Mean -0.222246
Standard dev 0.386997
Max value 11.3751
Min value -0.258899

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 901
Mean -16.1130
Standard dev 5.18299
Max value 138.098
Min value -17.9368

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 901
Mean 8.17380
Standard dev 14.4022
Max value 10.6158
Min value -423.286

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 901
Mean 0.149407
Standard dev 0.531865
Max value 0.879402
Min value -13.5055

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 900
Mean 18.4466
Standard dev 0.738546
Max value 20.2178
Min value 16.7730

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 333.102

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 901
Mean 161.566
Standard dev 0.967985
Max value 163.198
Min value 158.147

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 181.062

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems. Pitch and yaw are only displayed for flight A480, where specific manoeuvres were used to test the response of the NO_x inlets.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument “the fluorescence water vapour sensor”.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm³) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μ m to 3.00 μ m, to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μ m diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **CO:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = (k_3 j_4 [\text{O}_3] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]) / (k_5 [\text{M}] (j_6 + k_7 + [\text{OH}] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $\text{O}(^1\text{D}) + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{OH}$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $\text{O}(^1\text{D}) + \text{M} \rightarrow \text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{M}$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $\text{OH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HO}_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $\text{O}_3 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{O}(^1\text{D}) + \text{O}_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{OH} + \text{OH}$

j_4 , j_6 and $[\text{OH}]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Laura Cardenas (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters were not recorded on MRF's data recording system and are therefore not available as part of this data summary. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **PAN ECGC's:** Data are not included in this report but will be made available at a later date. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).

ARASF

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